

Biological Connectivity Patterns as a Blueprint for Efficient Neural Architectures in Reinforcement Learning

Artificial neural networks (ANNs) are the driving force behind many of today's technologies, but they often demand huge computational power. However, biological nervous systems are incredibly efficient, achieving high performance with far fewer resources. This research explores whether we can make ANNs more efficient by drawing inspiration from the clever design of biological neural networks. We tested a bio-inspired model, Neural Circuit Architectural Priors (NCAP), against Multi-Layer Perceptrons (MLPs), a common type of ANN, of varying sizes and connectivity in a reinforcement learning task, aiming to find architectures that best balance efficiency and performance. Our results show that NCAP, with far fewer parameters, performed just as well as larger, more complex MLPs. We also found that smaller, well-connected MLPs often outperform larger, poorly-connected ones, emphasizing the crucial role of connectivity in neural networks. These results suggest that the sparse, structured connectivity of biological neural networks offers an effective strategy for building efficient and high-performing ANNs.